

DETERMINATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS INDICATORS OF OFLOSAN AND ALISERYL WS ANTIBIOTICS IN PREVENTING COLIBACTERIOSIS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a number of current information on the prevalence of colibacillosis, a disease that is currently common and has a high incidence among young chickens kept in poultry farms in the Fergana region, the factors and causes of the disease, its economic damage, diagnostics, and elimination of the disease. In addition, the main content of the article is to describe the results of experiments using the antibiotics Oflosan, a product of the Russian Federation, and Aliseryl WS, a product of the Netherlands, in order to prevent the occurrence and spread of colibacillosis among young chickens, and to determine the effectiveness indicators and introduce an effective antibiotic into production.

Relevance of the topic. Poultry farming is considered one of the most profitable sectors of the livestock sector, and a number of farmers and peasant farms, as well as family entrepreneurs who began to operate in the context of economic reforms during the past period, are also preferring this sector. Because one egg-laying hen lays an average of 320-340 eggs per year, and a meat-laying chick gains 45-55 grams per day, it brings good income to entrepreneurs. The created conditions and opportunities impose specific tasks and great responsibilities on livestock specialists, as well as on poultry industry specialists and scientific researchers. The existing potential and production reserves in poultry farming are not being fully utilized. An important task in this regard is the healthy maintenance and growth of poultry and increasing its productivity. The results of the conducted research show that significant economic damage to poultry farming is caused by some infectious and invasive diseases, as well as shortcomings in the care and feeding of poultry. In particular, the mortality rate among poultry infected with colibacillosis is up to 75%. Therefore, one of the important tasks of today is to study the epidemiology, characteristics of the course and diagnostic methods of colibacillosis in poultry, and to develop modern methods of treatment and prevention. Since the metabolism in the body is intensive during the disease, it is advisable to feed the birds with a full-fledged diet.

When chickens are raised industrially, they are kept in large numbers in confined spaces, on bedding or in wire cages under artificial lighting. Chicks that hatch from incubation are vaccinated against infectious diseases based on a preventive vaccination schedule from the day they are one day old, once a week until they reach 120 days of age, that is, until they are transferred to a group of adult chickens. Ready-made feeds are distributed using machinery and mechanical devices. Because during illness, E. coli-Escherichia coli develops in the intestinal tract, which prevents the absorption of nutrients, and due to the difficulty of absorption processes, they lag behind in growth and development. In the future, the productivity of such poultry will be low. The cost of their treatment will increase, causing economic damage to the farm. Therefore, it is an urgent task of the veterinary service to constantly improve the study, prevention, and treatment of this disease, to use antibiotics in accordance with the sensitivity of the pathogens, and to prevent it, to maintain the number of poultry and achieve high productivity.

The purpose of the study: To determine the effectiveness of the antibiotic Oflosan compared to other antibiotics in preventing colibacillosis.

Research methods. In order to determine the effectiveness of the antibiotic Oflosan, 45 70-day-old young chickens of the "LOMANN SENDI" breed were selected and divided into 3 groups of 15 heads. The first experimental group was given the antibiotic Oflosan, and the second experimental group was given the antibiotic Aliseryl ws. The effectiveness of the antibiotics was determined based on the survival rate of the young chickens in the experimental groups and the increase in live weight.

Materials and methods of the study. Preventive measures in the research process were carried out among young chickens kept at the "IPAK YO'LI PARRANDA" farm in Furkat district of Fergana region.

Antibiotics used: - Oflosan - contains ofloxacin.

Application - for oral administration with water. 1 ml of the drug is dissolved in 1 liter of water and given for 3-5 days. Russian Federation, product of OOO "Aptsenna".

- Aliseryl ws - contains oxytetracycline.

Application - for oral administration with water. 1 g of the drug is dissolved in 1 liter of water and given for 5-7 days. Product of the Netherlands.

To carry out scientific research on this topic in farm conditions, 45 young chickens of the "LOMANN SENDI" breed aged 70 days were initially selected and divided into 3 groups of 15 heads. Young chickens in each group were also kept in farm conditions, and the first experimental group was given Oflosan antibiotic 1ml + 1 liter of water mixed for 5 days.

Young chickens in the second experimental group were given Aliseryl ws antibiotic 1 gr + 1 liter of water mixed for 7 days.

Young chickens in the third experimental group served as a control group for comparison.

Then, the clinical condition and growth and development of young chickens in the experimental group were analyzed in comparison with the birds in the control group. Young chickens in these groups, where practical testing experiments were conducted, were regularly monitored.

Research results: When the first experimental group was given Oflosan antibiotic, the survival rate of young chickens was 100 percent, and the increase in live weight was 127.5 percent.

When the second experimental group was treated with the antibiotic Aliseryl ws, the survival rate of young chickens was 86 percent, and the increase in live weight was 125.8 percent.

The survival rate of young chickens in the third control group was 53 percent, and the increase in live weight was 78.5 percent.

The effectiveness of Oflosan and Aliseryl ws antibiotics in preventing colibacillosis at the "IPAK YO'LI PARRANDA" farm in Furqat district of Fergana region

T/r	Name of groups	Name of drugs	Dose and method of application	Number of chickens	Persistence (in heads)	Persistence (in %)
1	Experiment	Oflosan	1 ml-1 liter of water	15	15	100
2	Experiment	Aliseryl ws	1 gr – 1 liter of water	15	13	86
3	Control	-	-	15	8	53

Thus, the survival rate of young chickens in the first experimental group was 100%, which was 47% higher than the control group that did not receive antibiotics.

In the second experimental group, the survival rate of young chickens was 86%, which was 33% higher than the control group that did not receive antibiotics.

Conclusions. Keeping young chickens in buildings that meet zoohygienic requirements in poultry farms, improving the quality of feeding and fulfilling sanitary requirements are important tasks in preventing the occurrence of colibacillosis.

- When the antibiotic Oflosan was used in production conditions to prevent colibacillosis in poultry, the survival rate of young chickens was recorded at 100%. - It should be noted that, taking into account that the antibiotic Oflosan not only increased the survival rate of chicks and hens, but also had a positive effect on their live weight gain and normal growth and development, it is recommended to use this treatment in poultry farms to prevent and treat colibacillosis.

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